

Bilbut Security Tools

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Abstract:

Real Time Encryption Method (RTEM) is better than solutions in current market in these ways: messages can be divided into parts in real time. It can and should use a main "brain" (such as Artificial Intelligence) to coordinate processes and results (this coordination is not necessary but recommended). Message is never sent, so there is no message to decrypt. As secure as modern encryption systems, according to mathematics. Really difficult to decrypt by attackers because RTEM is always changing (like a new password from time to time) and these changes do not require a new password, so it easier and safer for users.

It can be used for the emerging Artificial Intelligence (AI) market such as in the Voice Search feature of search engines (Siri, Alexa, Bixby, etc.), which is around the corner. It also can be used to encrypt two-way communications such as chats, group chats and private conversations. Also, Real Time Encryption Method can be used in protecting a private network. These are just a few examples.

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Kim System: Quick Introduction

Kim System sets up the rules to transmission of messages.

It is important to note that Kim System by itself is vulnerable, and I would not like to call it “cipher” because of its weakness.

However, when implemented by the Real Time Encryption Method, it brings more security.

Further chapters bring new additions and adaptations to Kim System.

What the general idea behind Kim System:

1. The numbers from the photo above in the form (x, y) are the coordinates of a randomly selected pixels.
2. Pixels are denoted as a little red dot in the picture.
3. All pixels have colors. For example, pixel $(83, 78)$ has a dark blue color.
4. All colors are to be expressed in HTML Color Codes.

Please visit the link below to get a better understanding of HTML Color Codes.

<http://www.computerhope.com/htmcolor.htm>

What is the ToF (Table of Frequencies)?

1. For example, take pixel $(416, 642)$.
2. Being pixel $(416, 642)$ the center of a circle with a radius of 20 pixels.
3. Say that all pixels located within the circle represent letter A.

4. Then pixel (416, 642) and (418, 644) represent letter A.
5. All pixels inside the circle represent letter A.

Important Notes:

1. Circle can be replaced by a square, rectangle, triangle or any other closed surface.
2. Any ASCII character can be used. I suggest using the printable ASCII characters.

Transmission Protocol

1. Above picture is a ToF in which each square represents character.
2. ToF must be overlapped over the photo (beach).
3. Photo can be any photo.

Special Abilities of Kim System

Kim System can be divided at least in two (2) parts: ToF and Photo.

The above is intended to be a security procedure.

Kim System does not send an encrypted message itself because it only sends coordinates, which means nothing to an unauthorized third-party person.

With this, there is less chance for capturing samples of the transmissions and try brute force.

Additional Steps

1. Where characters go, let's call them closed surfaces, cannot be an open surface (from the definition of open/closed surface in geometry).
2. Closed surfaces are: triangles, squares, rectangles, trapezoids, parallelograms, circles, ellipses, any other unregular shape, etc.
3. Never mix closed surfaces.
4. Closed surfaces cannot be superposed over other closed surfaces.
5. Characters should repeat at least once.
6. There must be at least one character inside the closed surfaces for each character in the message.

How does it work?

- a. Let's say that we want to transmit message SOS.
- b. We have three closed surfaces over a photo representing letters S and O.
- c. We select two pixels from closed surface that represents letter S.
- d. We select one pixel from closed surface that represents letter O.
- e. We order pixels in the order letters appear in the message: First S, then O and finally S again.
- f. We do (Coordinates of Pixel S) (Coordinates of Pixel O) (Coordinates of Pixel S).
- g. We send the three coordinates.
- h. Receiver takes the three coordinates and replaces them with their representation.
- i. Receiver must have same ToF and photo.

Transference of Files and Streams

1. Streams of audio and/or video can be sent if all characters inside shapes are zeroes and ones.
2. Result is that only coordinates are sent.
3. Digital files can be sent out this way.

Fixing Security Gaps

I realized that there are a few security gaps:

1. The length of the message is shown when transmitting a message.
2. For example: (500, 80) (60, 700) (100, 678) (234, 345) is a message of four (4) letters, which could be *home*, *good*, etc.
3. If ToF is a diagram (drawing) and has the right dimensions, then message could be decrypted without having the Kim System (1).

It is curious because these two problems above complement each other.

Interference Factor

In order to solve problem #2, the best solution is to send ordered triple in the following form:

- a. [X, Y, HTML Color Code of pixel at (X, Y)].
- b. Following previous example, new message would be (500, 80, 1000) (60,700, 3000) (100, 678, 10000) (234,345, 15000)

Does the message can be decoded without the Kim System (1)?

With each character of the message, multiple **fake** ordered triples are sent.

- Fake = Localization of pixel is out of the dimensions of photo.
- Fake = HTML Color Code from pixel is wrong.
- Fake = Both choices above.

Will 84 ordered triples change the meaning of the original message?

- a. If Kim System (1) ToF are present, it would be easy to differentiate between fake and true ordered triples.
- b. If an ordered triple does not meet the criteria, then it would be deleted and not taken into account.

Important Note:

- a. The more interference factor, the better.
- b. The above applies to large and short messages but specially to small messages.
- c. **Please remember that when I wrote about the interference factor, it was mostly because I was assuming that ToF was known by a third-party. This is why ToF and Kim System (1) need to be stored safely.**

Please do not allow attackers use the system to their favor: For this reason, Kim System (1) and ToF should be protected by passwords or simply saved on the cloud (Amara).

Ben System

This idea comes from my broken car CD player and from some mathematics.

I will divide the concept into two.

First part is as follows:

- 1) Imagine that there is a constantly repeating chain of zeroes and ones that starts again once the bit string ends.
- 2) In other words, imagine a song that is being constantly repeated by a radio station.
- 3) Then you can listen to the song with a not-broken FM radio.
- 4) The song is the sequence of zeroes and ones (analogy).

Above part is from the point of view of the signal sender.

Second part consists in that the receptor's equipment is broken and only can receive or reproduce the signal at intermittent times.

This way, from the original sequence of zeroes and ones or signal, a new sequence can be formed.

- 1) Sender's sequence is 010101010111010101111010101
- 2) It takes sender three (3) seconds to send the sequence to receptor.
- 3) Let's say that receptor's equipment was working for 1.9 seconds in total.
- 4) What receptor receives is 010101010111010 (new sequence).
- 5) Receptor's equipment is alive during the following intervals: [0.0,1.5], [1.9,2.0], [2.7,3.0].

A new sequence was derived from the original sequence.

In terms of software, working intervals of the radio are set by a mathematical function such as:

- a. Square root of a positive integer.
- b. Cubic root of an integer.
- c. nth root of a (+) integer.

Let's consider the simplest mathematical operation: $\text{sqrt}(x)$.

Imagine that the sequence is being transmitted repeatedly.

Software starts to count in terms of positive integers.

- a. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 ...
- b. The above sequence are seconds in my case.

Every time that the square root of the number in sequence is a whole number, then the equipment works and receives one digit. This way the new sequence is being created.

Special Ability of Ben System

The special ability of Ben System is to create images from the sequence of zeroes and ones.

- 1) The first step should be creating the first sequence of zeroes and ones (24 bits).
- 2) Convert binary numbers into a decimal and find its HTML Color.
- 3) This color is going to belong to pixel (0,0) -> (wide, length).
- 4) Sequence is erased.
- 5) Create a new sequence.
- 6) Convert to decimal and find its HTML Color.
- 7) That color should be added to pixel (0,1).
- 8) Repeat previous steps and create pixel (0,2).
- 9) Repeat until desired image size is met.

Conversion and Transition System

Definitions from the Dictionary:

- a. **Transition:** *the process or a period of changing from one state or condition to another.*
- b. **Conversion:** *the process of changing or causing something to change from one form to another.*

Transition vs. Conversion

Technical Definitions:

- a. T (Total) = length of password.
- b. Z_i = specific character.
- c. Conversion (C): changing table before making the step of a transition.
- d. Transition (T): changing the column sizes of the table.

Important Notes:

- a. There are multiple conversions in a single transition.
- b. In other words, there are many transformations in a single set of column size.

Previous Instructions:

- a. It needed a bunch of characters.
- b. Original design of this System consists of 95 blocks of random ASCII printable characters.

Let's take the following password as an example.

I L O V E M Y H O M E

1) First step is a transition:

- a. Take the first pair of letters: I L
- b. Values of I and L are their respective ASCII decimal value.
- c. Always first letter represents the X-axis and second letter represents Y-axis.

									I	
Z ₁₁	Z ₂₁	Z ₃₁	Z ₄₁	Z ₅₁	Z ₆₁	Z ₇₁	Z ₈₁	...	Z _{I1}	
Z ₁₂	Z ₂₂	Z ₃₂	Z ₄₂	Z ₅₂	Z ₆₂	Z ₇₂	Z ₈₂	...	Z _{I2}	
Z ₁₃	Z ₂₃	Z ₃₃	Z ₄₃	Z ₅₃	Z ₆₃	Z ₇₃	Z ₈₃	...	Z _{I3}	
Z ₁₄	Z ₂₄	Z ₃₄	Z ₄₄	Z ₅₄	Z ₆₄	Z ₇₄	Z ₈₄	...	Z _{I4}	
Z ₁₅	Z ₂₅	Z ₃₅	Z ₄₅	Z ₅₅	Z ₆₅	Z ₇₅	Z ₈₅	...	Z _{I5}	
Z ₁₆	Z ₂₆	Z ₃₆	Z ₄₆	Z ₅₆	Z ₆₆	Z ₇₆	Z ₈₆	...	Z _{I6}	
Z ₁₇	Z ₂₇	Z ₃₇	Z ₄₇	Z ₅₇	Z ₆₇	Z ₇₇	Z ₈₇	...	Z _{I7}	
...										
L	Z _{1L}	Z _{2L}	Z _{3L}	Z _{4L}	Z _{5L}	Z _{6L}	Z _{7L}	Z _{8L}	...	Z _{IL}

- a. The above table represents the first transition.
- b. Please note that transitions and conversions take password as the reference.

Transitions always go from left to right, except when there are no more characters to the right. Here is an example:

Table of Transitions:

Transition	Transition Number
(I, L)	1
(L, O)	2
(O, V)	3
(V, E)	4
(E, M)	5
(M, Y)	6
(Y, H)	7
(H, O)	8
(O, M)	9
(M, E)	10
(E, I)	11
(I, L)	12

- 2) Second step are conversions:
 - a. Direction is the opposite way: from left to right.
 - b. Conversion is equal the decimal value of the ASCII character previous to the first letter in a given transition.

Table of Conversions:

Conversion	Value	Conversion Number
Decimal value of ASCII (E)	69	1
Decimal value of ASCII (M)	77	2
Decimal value of ASCII (O)	79	3
Decimal value of ASCII (H)	72	4
Decimal value of ASCII (Y)	89	5
Decimal value of ASCII (M)	77	6
Decimal value of ASCII (E)	69	7
Decimal value of ASCII (V)	86	8
Decimal value of ASCII (O)	79	9
Decimal value of ASCII (L)	76	10
Decimal value of ASCII (I)	73	11
Decimal value of ASCII (E)	69	12

Here is an example of the conversions:

Resuming:

How does it work?

1. Following the given example:
 - a. Let's do the first transition: (I, L).
 - b. Then conversion value is 69.
2. Then do 69 conversions and go ahead with the next transition.
3. Repeat this process.

Important Note:

- The Conversion and Transition System is not intended to end its process of operations. This is because its implementation in the Real Time Encryption Method does require this System to never end working.

Additional Security

1. On each time doing a single conversion, do this:

a. In the above example, do this 69 times.

$$P = [(((C + T_{next} + C_{next})^{((T_{next+1}) + (C_{next+1}))} + Z_{IL}) * C * C_{next} + 1) \bmod (Z + 1)]$$

If $P < Y$, then

$$P = [(((C + T_{next} + C_{next})^{((T_{next+1}) + (C_{next+1}))} + Z_{IL}) * C * C_{next} + 1) \bmod (Z + 1)] + Y$$

Where C_{next} is the same as:

- A) Please remember that we are doing this single conversion 69 times.
- B) Follow the table below and further description after that:

Time Doing Single Conversion (C = 69)	C_{next} is equal to:
1	77
2	79
3	72
4	89
5	77
6	69
7	86
8	79
9	76
10	73
11	69
12	77

1. There is a cycle! So that C_{next} is always equal to the next transition from the previous one.
 - a. This is done following the Conversion pattern of always to the left.

Where T_{next} is the same as:

1. Same way as in Conversions but with Transitions.
 - a. Remember that Transitions go to the right always.

Time Doing Single Conversion (C = 69)	T_{next} is equal to:
1	76
2	79
3	86
4	69
5	77
6	89
7	72
8	79
9	77

10	69
11	73
12	76

Where $C_{next + 1}$ and $T_{next + 1}$ are the same as:

1. The C_{next} and T_{next} of C_{next} and T_{next} respectively.
 - a. C_{next} of C_{next}
 - b. T_{next} of T_{next}
2. Of course, values of I and L change according to the given transition.
3. Y = Initial value, which in this case is 32 (first printable ASCII character - decimal system).
 - a. This value changes in the Real Time Encryption Method, and is zero (0) in the case of RTEM.
4. Z = Maximum value.
 - a. In this case it is 126 (to prove a theory).
 - b. In the Real Time Encryption Method this value changes and it is the equivalent to HTML white color: #FFFFFF (hexadecimal system) or 16777215 (decimal system), and this is to be able to adapt the Conversion and Transition System (CT System) to Ben System.
 - c. In case of simply using CT System normally such as to generate a hash, then $Z = Z_{IL}$
5. Please keep in mind that P should be a non-negative integer (including zero) or its equivalent in other numeric systems.

Push to the right Z_{11} and bring P to the place where was Z_{11} . Do this 69 times in this example:

- **Delete Z_{IL}**

									I	
P	Z_{11}	Z_{21}	Z_{31}	Z_{41}	Z_{51}	Z_{61}	Z_{71}	...	Z_{81}	
Z_{I1}	Z_{12}	Z_{22}	Z_{32}	Z_{42}	Z_{52}	Z_{62}	Z_{72}	...	Z_{82}	
Z_{I2}	Z_{13}	Z_{23}	Z_{33}	Z_{43}	Z_{53}	Z_{63}	Z_{73}	...	Z_{83}	
Z_{I3}	Z_{14}	Z_{24}	Z_{34}	Z_{44}	Z_{54}	Z_{64}	Z_{74}	...	Z_{84}	
Z_{I4}	Z_{15}	Z_{25}	Z_{35}	Z_{45}	Z_{55}	Z_{65}	Z_{75}	...	Z_{85}	
Z_{I5}	Z_{16}	Z_{26}	Z_{36}	Z_{46}	Z_{56}	Z_{66}	Z_{76}	...	Z_{86}	
Z_{I6}	Z_{17}	Z_{27}	Z_{37}	Z_{47}	Z_{57}	Z_{67}	Z_{77}	...	Z_{87}	
...										
L	Z_{I7}	Z_{1L}	Z_{2L}	Z_{3L}	Z_{4L}	Z_{5L}	Z_{6L}	Z_{7L}	...	Z_{8L}

In case of a Transition, do the same as in a conversion but...

$$P = (Z_{IL} + P_{IL - 1}) \bmod Z$$

If $P < Y$,

$$P = [(Z_{IL} + P_{IL - 1}) \bmod Z] + Y$$

Please note that I and L change according to the given transition.

Additional Security 2

- a. Random blocks sizes of 10 to 20 ASCII printable characters.
- b. Apply the above to each of the 95 blocks.

Example of a single block:

A1B2C3D4E5F6H7I9

Please note that Z_{xy} = single block, in which the values x and y change.

How would it be when doing the second transition and on?

- a. Think about the table as if it were a list.
- b. Before the second transition, convert table to a list.
- c. Supposing that the table, after all conversions take place, looks like this.

a. List should be as follows:

Z₁₁, Z₂₁, Z₃₁, Z₄₁, Z₅₁, Z₆₁, Z₇₁, Z₈₁, Z₁₂, Z₂₂, Z₃₂, Z₄₂, Z₅₂, Z₆₂, Z₇₂, Z₈₂, Z₁₃, Z₂₃, Z₃₃, Z₄₃, Z₅₃, Z₆₃, Z₇₃, Z₈₃, Z₁₄, Z₂₄, Z₃₄, Z₄₄, Z₅₄, Z₆₄, Z₇₄, Z₈₄, Z₁₅, Z₂₅,

Z₃₅, Z₄₅, Z₅₅, Z₆₅, Z₇₅, Z₈₅, Z_{I5}, Z₁₆, Z₂₆, Z₃₆, Z₄₆, Z₅₆, Z₆₆, Z₇₆, Z₈₆, Z_{I6}, Z₁₇, Z₂₇, Z₃₇,
Z₄₇, Z₅₇, Z₆₇, Z₇₇, Z₈₇, ..., Z_{I7}, Z_{1L}, Z_{2L}, Z_{3L}, Z_{4L}, Z_{5L}, Z_{6L}, Z_{7L}, Z_{8L}

1. Next step is to set the new X-axis and Y-axis according to the values of the new transition.
2. Take the decimal value of the ASCII character of the first character (from the password) of the new transition. This makes the X-axis.
3. Next step is dividing the list after every X-axis value and adding those new divisions into the new table (rows).
4. If the number of blocks in a single row are not equal to the X-axis value, then take as much as needed from the original list. Begin with the first block of the list in this case and go on until all rows are equal to each other.
5. At this point, the new transition is set up.
6. Next step is doing conversions.

Special Case of Transition

In this case:

- a. On the second letter find the next ASCII printable character.

Things to Consider:

- 1) Password should be at least ten (10) characters long.
- 2) Use uppercase, lowercase, numbers and special characters.
- 3) Less than four (4) equal and consecutive characters in the password.

Types of Attacks

Important Note:

- a. In the Real Time Encryption Method (RTEM), lists are never sent out of the Users' "client" software.
- b. However, what is known as "list" in the CT System is also known as Kim System (2) in RTEM.
- c. So, this is why I always start with knowing list because list is going to be the file (Kim System (2)), and file is the best way for attackers to try to guess password.
- d. Here are different types of attacks:

A) Knowing the original LIST and trying to get password.

Let's take a look to a single transition MN

- Both characters can be 1 out of 95.
- Possibility of knowing them both is 1 out of 95²

First time doing the same single conversion, attackers have to guess:

- a) C
- b) C_{next}
- c) T_{next}
- d) C_{next+1}
- e) T_{next+1}

So, the number of possibilities for guessing the value of P are 1 out of 95^5 .

But because all five values change the second time doing the same single conversion and on...

The possibilities are 1 out of $95^5 * F$, where F is the number of times doing a single conversion.

The number of times doing a single conversion varies between 32 and 126 inclusive, but let's say that they 60 as an average.

Possibilities for a single conversion: 1 out of 95^{300} .

Without forgetting conversion and transitions, the total possibilities for a single transition are: 1 out of 95^{302} .

Remember that this was for a single Transition.

Supposing that there are ten (10) Transitions, possibilities would be:

1 out of $(95^{302})^{10} = 1$ out of $(95^{3020}) = 5$ out 10^{5972}

B) Attempting to find password using block size (knowing List).

- If all blocks' sizes were the same, let's say 10, there would be $95 \times 10 = 950$ characters.
- Then possibilities would be:

1 out of $95^{95} = 1$ out of 7×10^{187}

This is extremely weak!

- However, blocks sizes differ in sizes randomly between ten (10) to twenty (20) characters.

This way this type of attack would be really difficult to perform due to *the unknown size of blocks*.

However, this changes in the adaptation for Ben System (RTEM) because maximum value is 16777215, which is 8 characters long.

- Let's say that there is an average of five (5) characters per block:
- Then total number of characters are: 95 times 5 = 475 characters.

C) Knowing List and trying to obtain password (Brute Force).

Please note that block values change on every conversion. However, ...

- 95 Blocks.
- Each block ranges from ten (10) to twenty (20) characters.
- There would be between $95 \times 10 = 950$ characters and $95 \times 20 = 1920$ characters.
- Possibility to find a character is 1 out of 95.

Possibilities of brute force ranges from 1 out of (95^{950}) to 1 out of (95^{1920}) .

However, in the case of the adaptation to RTEM, possibilities are (average): 1 out of 10^{475}

There may be other types of attacks but these are the ones that come to my mind.

Like I always say: "Best way to crack down a cryptographic system is using the system against itself. So, do not get to that point."

This is basically the Conversion and Transition System.

Real Time Encryption Method

Techniques used:

- a. Kim System
- b. Ben System
- c. Conversion and Transition System

Purpose:

- a. Idea is to use all previous methods discussed into a working system.

Diagram (Please refer to Figure4.jpg):

Further explanation of diagram:

- a. **Blue:** Engines that must be already set up in the users' systems. This practice is commonly known as "Client" software or as "front-end".
- b. **Green:** This is data, which must be synchronized through Amara.
- c. **Gray:** Amara is the cloud and must be in constant communication with each user.

Quick Introduction:

1. Kim System (2): Must be bunch of digital data such as zeroes and ones. I cannot think of anything better than a song (.mp3). It could any other computer's file such as a photo or a calculator or game executable.
2. Kim System (1): Transmission protocol between each users' systems.
3. Ben System: Converts the bunch of zeroes and ones from the Kim System (2) into the picture needed for Kim System (1).

4. Password: Amara can setup password or can be set by each user or can be set between each user using Diffie-Hellman Key Exchange Method.
5. ToF: This stands for Table of Frequencies and must be set by Amara.
6. Conversion and Transitions System: Makes sure the that that Ben System uses is unique. This system uses the password to make sure that data generated by Ben System is the same on each User's systems.

Ben System:

The best implementation of Ben System is to create Kim System (1) based on Kim System (2).

From attached guide of Ben System this may be a change to how the system works. It is not because this is only an implementation of Ben System.

What Ben System needs to work? (Please refer to attached documents about Ben System)

- It needs two inputs to work: a mathematical function and the sequence of zeroes and ones.
- Mathematical function has to be preset.

How the implementation works?

1. The new implementation is based on how Ben System delivers results.
2. Following the analogy of Ben System, every time mathematical function fires, then:
 - a. (A) Stop listening to the sequence of zeroes and ones.
 - b. (B) Collect current sequence.
3. It is important to note that every time that the mathematical function (analogy) fires, then Ben System would be collecting every digit that comes from the same sequence.
4. This leads to create a new sequence of zeroes and ones.
5. This is the function of Ben System, and it should do it always.
6. Moving on, sequences cannot be longer than 24 digits because:
 - a. White color, #FFFFFF, is the maximum and it has 24 digits when converted to zeroes and ones.
7. In case that the limit of 24 digits is reached before a mathematical function fires, Ben System does not wait for the mathematical function and automatically collects a new sequence.
8. **In fact, collecting 24 digits is the mathematical function.**

From where does Ben System get the sequence?

1. Right from the Conversion and Transition System.
2. After all the conversions and transitions are performed under the specific password, then translate the Table into a sequence.
3. Table after operations (example):

A B C D E F G H I J K

L M N O P Q R S T U

V W X Y Z 1 2 3 4 5

- To this sequence:

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ12345 (and so on)

1. As you can see there are not spaces in the new sequence, unless it exists in the Table.
2. And, as it is needed by Ben System, each character must be converted to binary following ASCII rules.
3. Since the Conversion and Transition System should use up to ASCII character 126 as the maximum and ASCII character 32 as the minimum (Printable ASCII characters), I suggest converting each character to eight (8) binary digits. This practice includes adding zeroes to the left.

What are we doing up to now?

1. If you have not noticed yet, each sequence of 24 digits collected is a pixel. We are creating Kim System (1). I mean, we are creating a picture.
2. I have not decided what would be the dimensions of the picture. They could be 100px by 100px or any other size such as 350px by 350px.

To where are we going with all these?

- a. When the ToF (Table of Frequencies) is overlapped over Kim System (1), there must be a color for every pixel, and so, we can complete Kim System requirement for sending ordered triples.
- b. Let's remember:

Ordered triple = (A, B, HTML Pixel Color), where (A, B) are coordinates to locate pixels on the Kim System (1).

Please refer to Kim System documents.

Important Notes:

1. Depending on the sizes of Kim System, Ben System will take more or less time to create Kim System (1).
2. There should not be messages sent / received while there is not a Kim System (1) available.
3. First time creating Kim System (1) is the only downtime because:
 - a. While another Kim System (1) is being created, users can use the previous Kim System (1).
 - b. Once a new Kim System (1) is available, it replaces the old Kim System (1), and Ben System starts creating another Kim System (1). **This process never stops.**
 - c. **I suggest that, at most, after three (3) Kim System (1) are created, the Conversion and Transition System is activated. I would do it after two (2) Kim System (1) are created.**
4. The above is a cycle and must be going on even if users are not sending / receiving messages.
5. **Cycle never stops.**
6. Change Kim System (1) after certain time periods:
 - a. After too many transmissions.
 - b. Upon request by any of the users (limit the number user can request this).
 - c. After too much of being active.

Possible complications ad solutions:

1. If User A's Conversion and Transition System has done three (3) entire operations, while User B's Conversion and Transition System has done only two (2) entire operations, I would say that there should be complications.
2. This is why it is imperative to have User A's and User B's systems ("clients") synchronized.
3. There are two (2) ways having this done:
 - a. Through communications between each User's clients.
 - b. Using a third-party tool ("cloud") that I use to refer to as Amara.
4. I strongly recommend using Amara for two (2) reasons:
 - a. In today's days, cloud technology is ever time more used than ever before. It should not be difficult to implement such a thing as Amara.
 - b. Amara not necessarily needs to be connected to internet. There are many implementations of the Real Time Encryption Method.
 - c. Please refer to the Conversion and Transition System to recall the way it works. Like Ben System, the Conversion and Transition System works as it is explained originally but with some adjustments.

Depending on the way Kim System (2) is viewed as the Conversion and Transition System's standard, I can suggest a few things.

1. Kim System (2) can be viewed as:
 - a. Only zeroes and ones:
 - i. Treat every eight (8) consecutive digits as if they were one. So that when conversions and transitions, they move amongst the table as one.
 - b. Hex values:
 - i. Treat each one (1) consecutive character as one. Then convert to binary.
 - c. If using in the table a generated bunch of random numbers and letters, please treat each character as one character. Then, when using Ben System, convert to eight (8) digit binary each character before Ben System uses it.
2. It is important to go converting just as Ben System needs. This way, a lot of computer operations are saved than if the entire chain were to be converted at once.
3. I strongly recommend using a digital file as the Kim System (2) and not random sequences because random sequences can be over, while it is extremely strange to have a single .mp3 song, for example, to end soon.
4. It is amazing the number of zeroes and ones that can be found inside a single .mp3 song of about 4 Megabytes of size.

Step by Step Guide to Secure Communications:

- 1) User A and User B are connected to Amara.
- 2) Amara secures communications with both users using Diffie-Hellman Key Exchange Method and AES-256 bits (example).
- 3) Amara establishes:
 - a. Kim System (2)
 - b. Password
 - c. ToF

- 4) Conversion and Transition System completes an entire operation of transitions and conversions.
- 5) Ben System starts creating Kim System (1).
- 6) After Kim System (1) is created in both Users' systems:
 - a. Ben System starts creating another Kim System (1).
 - b. Every two (2) creations of Kim System (1), the Conversion and Transition System starts doing another operation.
- 7) As this previous cycle continues without interruption:
 - a. Users' systems overlap ToF over the Kim System (1).
 - b. Transmission protocol is stated by Kim System rules.
- 8) At this point, communication is safe, at least according to me.

This is basically the Real Time Encryption Method. I named it that way because it seemed to me that it was "alive" at the time I got the idea.

Bilbut Authentication Method

Username:

Password (1st):

Password (2nd):

Login Process:

- 1) Username is used to retrieve stored files.
 - a. These files are encrypted using a modern secure algorithm such as AES-256 bits.
 - b. Files contain an encrypted list from the Conversion and Transition System.
- 2) Second Password is used to decrypt (or attempt to) retrieved file (list).
- 3) Use first password to generate a hash using the decrypted file.
 - a. The Conversion and Transition System (CT System) is used as a hash here.
 - b. CT System needs a password, which is the First Password (1st).
 - c. Hash is generated using the CT System.
- 4) If generated hash coincides with the hash that username has stored in the system (platform), then ACCESS.
 - a. In modern systems a hash is stored for every username.
 - b. Then password entered is used to generate a hash and compare it with the one stored for the specific username.
 - c. If both coincides, then user has access to the system (platform).
 - d. This same way works Bilbut Authentication System.

Interference: Increasing list size:

1. Because in this case the Conversion and Transition System is used as a hash, there is no problem with increasing the list size.
 - a. A hash means that it is not intended to be processed in the opposite way: Only with encryption direction (no decryption is possible).

Please refer to the Conversion and Transition Method functioning...

- Every time that there is a Transition (T), let's increase the number of blocks in the list by one:

- 1) After moving Z_{IL} to the beginning of the table, copy (not moving) the following block like this:

- a. Copy to:
 - i. If $T_i < T_{i+1}$, then copy before Z_{IL}
 - ii. If $T_i > T_{i+1}$, then copy after Z_{IL}
- 2) Value of new block:
 - a. According to table (not list), value to copy is: $(Z_{IL} - I \text{ XOR } Z_{IL} - L) \text{ XOR } Z_{IL} - I - L$

- b. In case none of the above block values for the XOR operation are in binary system, then let's convert them this way:
 - i. $Z_{IL} - L = ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOP$ (example).
 - ii. Take binary of each character from their respective ASCII value.
 - iii. Let's use the first three (3) characters of the given block: ABC
 - iv. $A = 1000001$, $B = 1000010$, $C = 1000011$.
 - v. Then combine them in a single chain following the given order:
 - vi. $ABC = 100000110000101000011$
 - vii. There it is the binary number necessary for the XOR operation.
 - viii. Do the same for the three (3) blocks.
- The number of times to do this is every time there is a Transition (T).

More Things to Consider:

- 1) Both passwords cannot be equal.
- 2) At least 10 characters long as a standard of safety, but passwords can be as low as 8 characters long.
- 3) No more than two (2) equal characters consecutive.
- 4) Use uppercase, lowercase, numbers and special characters.
- 5) Less than four (4) equal and consecutive characters between each password.
- 6) Second password can be saved in the system (platform such as a browser or mobile app) but first password cannot be allowed to be saved: User must type in first password each time.
 - a. Programmatically make it possible.
- 7) Limit number of login attempts.

Recovery Options:

- 1) Forgot username:
 - a. Ask user to enter email and send username.
- 2) Forgot any of the two (2) passwords:
 - a. Enter username.
 - b. Verify email address.
 - c. Verify phone access.
 - d. User should be asked if he/she desires to make changes to any of the two (2) passwords (after successful verification of email and device).
 - i. Notify user of change.
 - ii. If user enters any of the fake passwords as any of the two passwords or as both passwords, account would be locked and security measures will be taken.
 - iii. Please refer to fake password.

Activation of Fake Password:

1. These are the actions to activate fake password:
 - a. Enter username.
 - b. Enter fake password as first, second or both passwords.
 - i. User only needs to enter fake password once. For the other password just use anything.

c. Try to login.

Please use fake password carefully.

Wrong vs. Fake:

1. User must set at least one fake password and choose what attackers see:
 - a. Mascot with message.
 - b. Message only.
 - c. Notifications: SMS, email, mail.
2. User must read accept policies regarding what will happen after a fake password is used.
3. However, a wrong password is a password that is not a fake password and only counts as a failed login attempt.

More Security:

1. Change hash and encrypted list:
 - a. from time to time.
 - b. upon user request.
 - i. User can schedule a change or even the platform.
2. These new hash and encrypted list are generated using the same passwords (1st and 2nd), unless:
 - a. Security breach.
 - b. Fake password.
3. in cases of fake password or security breach, change passwords instead of changing hash and list.
 - a. However, a password change leads to new hash and list anyways.